

Modern methods of teaching a foreign language to non-linguistic specialties

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Abstract: The new requirements for student education, require appropriate professional competence, including the ability to communicate in a foreign language and actualize research attention to different approaches, technologies, and conditions. the goal is to increase the quality of higher education. The article examines some innovative methods of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. Based on research, the author shows that there is a need for innovative pedagogical technologies that would be effective and promote the gradual development of the science of pedagogy and prepare students for future professional activities.

Keywords: modern methods, teaching methods for foreign language students, characteristics of teaching, active methods.

Today foreign languages are considered not only as a means of communication but mainly to stimulate the process of consciousness. Knowledge of foreign languages is a mandatory part of the professional training of modern specialists of every profile. Many aspects of the development of linguistic competence depend on the nature, content, and orientation of future expert training. In this regard, students of non-language departments deserve special attention. According to the requirements established as a result of learning, the student must communicate in a foreign language both orally and in writing on professional and everyday topics, improve his oral and written language. Students have different mental abilities,

different innate abilities, and different interests, so one of the most pressing problems in foreign language education is teaching a foreign language to students with different language abilities. One way to solve this problem is to use a differentiated approach to teaching foreign languages to students with different language learning. As years of practice show, modern methods of teaching foreign languages offer us a wide range of traditional and innovative concepts, methods, and technologies of the educational process. Curriculum developers and teachers prefer one or another method depending on the learning objectives, the number of students, the duration and intensity of the training course, and other conditions. In addition, each teaching method has its advantages and disadvantages, and the success of its implementation depends on the specific goals and conditions of education. In recent years, the role of a foreign language as a means of communication has grown significantly, which must be taken into account in language learning.

Several modern methods and approaches can be effective in teaching a foreign language to non-linguistic specialties. Some of these methods include:

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): This approach focuses on developing students' ability to communicate effectively in real-life situations. It emphasizes the use of authentic materials, group work, and interactive activities to promote language learning.
- Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT): In this approach, students are given tasks or projects to complete using the target language. This method encourages students to use the language in meaningful contexts and helps them develop their language skills through practical application.
- Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL): CLIL combines language learning with subject content, such as history, science, or mathematics. This approach allows students to learn both the target language and subject matter simultaneously, making the learning process more engaging and relevant.

- **Blended Learning:** Blended learning combines traditional classroom instruction with online resources and technology-based tools. This approach offers students a variety of resources and interactive activities to enhance their language learning experience.

By incorporating these modern methods into foreign language instruction for non-linguistic specialties, educators can create a dynamic and effective learning environment that caters to diverse learners' needs and preferences. The peculiarity of a foreign language is that we do not teach the basics of natural sciences, but skills and abilities, and this requires sufficient speaking practice. Materials and research methods oriented learning that takes into account the constantly changing requirements, and the achievements of pedagogical and psychological sciences. Several methods were used to solve the problems by the purpose of the research and to test the hypothesis experimentally: theoretical methods, analysis of scientific and methodological, psychological and pedagogical literature, study of research regulations, and program documentation. theme; empirical methods questioning, testing, discussion, pedagogical experiment, self-evaluation, actual evaluation, observation. Results and discussion The purpose of teaching a foreign language is not only to introduce students to the foreign language system, but mainly to teach them to use language as a means of communication. Therefore, the whole structure of the lessons and the methods used must correspond to the real communication situation, and the training must take place in the conditions of student communication. To ensure the results of foreign language learning, the teacher's work system must necessarily include the introduction of the following technologies: communicative learning technology, technology to understand the communicative meaning of the text, game technologies, cooperative learning technologies, project technologies, etc. The concept of technology is borrowed from the production area. In our opinion, the pedagogical methods of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university must be understood as a set of forms,

methods, teaching techniques, and learning tools systematically used in learning. The purpose of innovations in the field of education is to form the personality, and its capacity for scientific, technical, and innovative activities, and to update the content of the educational process.

In the sense of the pedagogical process, innovation means bringing something new to the goals, content, methods, and forms of teaching and education, organizing cooperation between teacher and student. Educational innovation refers to the possibility of introducing high-level scientific development into the educational process so that it enables the training of experts who can independently apply innovations during their scientific and practical careers. The development of innovative techniques for teaching foreign languages is due to the need to overcome the educational crisis, which would encourage the training of specialists in a new composition. The educational technology of the last century, which is based on the logic of science, with the principle "from knowledge to skills", should be formed into a technology based on the laws of the cognitive activity of students, which should strive for this. heights of professional, creative activity, the mental and moral performance of graduates. In the new educational paradigm, the student is an active subject of cognitive activity, who engages in dialogue with the teacher through new forms of organization of learning. Today's student is an active, creative person who must.

References:

1. Ahmed S.T.S. & Pawar S. (2018). Communicative competence in English as a Foreign Language: Its Meaning and the Pedagogical Considerations for its Development. *The Creative Launcher*, 2 (6), 302–312
2. David Nunan. *Communicative Language Teaching* – 2004
3. Nechaeva, E. I. (2017). Using the Internet in teaching a foreign language. *Proceedings from: Modern Technologies and Innovations in the Pedagogical System of Education: Collection of Scientific Papers on the Materials of the First International Scientific and Practical Conference*. Nizhniy Novgorod, Russia: Individual entrepreneur Krasnova Natalia Aleksandrovna

4. L.V. Yurkina, L.P. Krivshenko (2019) Pedagogy: Course book and practical training for academic bachelor's program. M.: Yurait, 2019. 400 p.
5. Hudayberganova E Modern methods and technologies of teaching foreign languages in a high school <https://moluch.ru/conf/phil/archive/178/10430/>